

PERSONALLY-ORIENTED APPROACH IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES.

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ABSTRACT

The article describes the approach of «personally-oriented» and analyze the content of positive effects of personally-oriented approach on foreign language teaching. When compared to traditional language teaching, cooperative language learning follows the development trend of language teaching methods and has significant advantages. Personally-oriented approach in foreign language classrooms provides students with the necessary academic and social skills. The paper demonstrates that personally-oriented approach benefits language learning in a variety of ways.

An analysis of pedagogical theory and practice allows us to conclude that the essence of the concept of "cooperation in the educational process" is considered from different positions. It is possible to single out a wide range of works devoted to cooperation as a joint activity of a teacher and students or students with each other. Various aspects of cooperation in the classroom, the conditions for the formation of the personality of students in the conditions of joint work were studied (V.A. Bezrukova, L.S. Savina, G.K. Selevko, Yu.V. Senko, S.A. Temina, N.K. Tikhomirova, R.Kh. Shakurov, etc.). It should be noted that "educational cooperation" is not the only term used by researchers to refer to this form of educational work (I.P. Fokina, G.A. Tsukerman). The following names are also used: "joint educational activity" (V.Ya. Lyaudis, A.K. Markova, T.A. Matis),

The organization of educational cooperation in the classroom can help the administration and teachers of the school to improve academic performance and teach students to communicate and work with each other students of different nationalities, social status and different genders. Educational cooperation makes it possible to create a democratic educational space. The interaction of schoolchildren at any age expands their comfort zone and helps to gain confidence in communication. The more students talk to each other and know about each other, the more tolerant they are of each other.

Educational cooperation is based on three principles:

- Simultaneous interaction: The more students talk to each other, the more they are involved in the learning process and the better they learn.

- Positive interdependence: The success of each team and each team member is not possible without the success and participation of everyone.

- Personal Responsibility: By taking responsibility for a specific part of the project - and getting graded for it - the student becomes accountable.

- "In-class learning collaboration expands students' comfort zone and develops the skills they need to communicate with other people," says Lucia Brooks, "And school is the perfect place to learn these skills."

But learning collaboration alone does not improve classroom relationships. You need to teach respect and tolerance towards others directly.

Allowing students to sit with whoever they want will place them among their closest friends within their existing personal comfort zone.

Simultaneous interaction.

In most cases, the teacher does the talking 80% of the time during the lesson. Simultaneous interaction makes it possible to speak to everyone, significantly increasing the productivity of study time for students. In addition to directly teaching a subject, such as a native language or a foreign language, students talk to each other over and over again, which increases their confidence before they have to answer in front of a whole class. You can also set a more specific task - to look into the eyes of the one you are talking to.

Working in a small group (four people), students solve the problem proposed by the teacher. Each of the four must know the answer as they will be asked to move to another group where only one of them will know the answer.

In any case, everyone should be given the opportunity to talk to as many people as possible.

Positive interdependence.

You can summarize this thought in a few words: "I need you, you need me." Individual success and group success are not possible without each other. In the middle of the school year, when students in the new class already know each other, you can focus on building team spirit. The teacher might say, "There are things you don't know about your neighbor." Then, using the Bingo cards and working in groups, the children ask each other questions: "What is your favorite dish?" or "What's your favorite show?" As usual, she must follow the rules - speak in full sentences and look the interlocutor in the eye.

The teacher should encourage the expression of personal disagreement and teach how to do it correctly and politely, constantly teaching students to express and accept criticism without becoming personal.

You can offer another game - "Who am I?". A piece of paper with the name of some famous character is pinned on the back. Working in pairs and asking each other questions, students guess who they are - Spider-Man, the Easter Bunny, or President Bush. And again, the main task is to create a friendly atmosphere.

The following trick can be used to rally teams. Invite the groups to answer the question: "If you were a superhero, who would you be and why?" or "If you were a car, what would you be and why?".

Students can also offer their own version, for example, "If you were something edible, what and why?". Some rudeness of students towards each other is not

excluded, but once again speaks of the vital importance of mutual communication between schoolchildren and building trusting and respectful relationships between them.

Personal responsibility

Personal responsibility is another fundamental principle of educational cooperation. Each student is responsible for his or her achievement, participation and involvement in the project. An example would be working in groups of four, say, in a math class. Solving the problem, students perform actions in turn on a large sheet of paper with markers. In a lesson of their native or foreign language, they read aloud one sentence at a time. At the same time, the group is interested in watching the actions of the partner. And so step by step, action by action. Seeing that something is going wrong, students are forced to react by offering their own solution or correcting the mistake. By doing this, they develop self-confidence, which is psychologically much easier in a small group than in front of a whole class. The teacher controls and, if necessary, corrects the process,

This technique is especially effective for students who have difficulty mastering the educational material. During the lesson, such students are fully involved in the learning process, they learn to listen to what others are saying. At the same time, they feel more successful and psychologically protected.

Mutually complementary, personal responsibility and team spirit are the key points of educational cooperation. For this technique to really work, the teacher must apply these strategies in every lesson, throughout the school year. The key to success lies in the positive development of

interpersonal relationships among trainees.

All scientists who deal with teaching foreign languages emphasize that in teaching foreign languages importance of the teacher's professional language competence, factors of accounting of educational subject's particularities and individual peculiarities of learners, especially motivation in learning foreign languages are equal. The process of teaching foreign languages consists of three equal components:

- the teacher and his professional skills;
- the learner and his aspiration;
- the subject which learner must acquire.

It is natural that in psychological-pedagogical analyses of education we must consider factors-components mentioned above. Thereupon in our opinion important factors and components of educational system are - psychological features of foreign language teachers; psychological features of learners of various age stages; psychological features of foreign language as educational subject; psychological analysis of speech activity as an object of mastering; pupil's educational activity in the process of learning foreign languages and the form of education.

Speaking about the factors which influence on successful learning foreign language it is necessary to note a close connection of psychology of teaching foreign language with psychological and pedagogical disciplines, particularly, with pedagogical psychology. All mentioned factors and components of education are the research subject of pedagogical psychology.

Pedagogical psychology - are the most important branches of psychology. The basis for allocation of this branch of

psychology is the psychological aspect of concrete activity of teaching and studying.

Pedagogical psychology is in close relationship with developmental and age psychology, which study 'age dynamics of person's mental development, ontogenesis of mental process and psychological quality of developing person'. Ontogenesis refers to the sequence of events involved in the development of an individual organism from its birth to its death. This developmental history often involves a move from simplicity to higher complexity. So all problems of development and age psychology are considered on the basis of accounting person's age features. Pedagogical and age psychology in their researching base on the theories of General Psychology, which opens the general psychological laws, studies mental processes, mental conditions and person's individual-psychological peculiarities.

Pedagogical psychology as independent branch started to form in the end of XIX century collecting experiences and achievements of pedagogical, psychological and psychophysical experiments and researches.

Pedagogical psychology includes - Educational Psychology, Upbringing Psychology and Teacher's Psychology.

In America this field of psychology is mainly called Educational Psychology.

Educational psychology is the study of how humans learn in educational settings, the effectiveness of educational interventions, the psychology of teaching, and the social psychology of schools as organizations. Educational psychology is concerned with how students learn and develop, often focusing on subgroups such as gifted children and those subject to specific disabilities. Although the terms

"educational psychology" and "school psychology" are often used interchangeably, researchers and theorists are likely to be identified in the US and Canada as educational psychologists, whereas practitioners in schools or school-related settings are identified as school psychologists. This distinction is however not made in the UK, where the generic term for practitioners is "educational psychologist".

Educational psychology can in part be understood through its relationship with other disciplines. It is informed primarily by psychology, bearing a relationship to that discipline analogous to the relationship between medicine and biology. Educational psychology in turn informs a wide range of specialties within educational studies, including instructional design, educational technology, curriculum development, organizational learning, special education and classroom management. Educational psychology both draws from and contributes to cognitive science and the learning sciences. In universities, departments of educational psychology are usually housed within faculties of education, possibly accounting for the lack of representation of educational psychology content in introductory psychology textbooks.

To understand the characteristics of learners in childhood, adolescence, adulthood, and old age, educational psychology develops and applies theories of human development. Often represented as stages through which people pass as they mature, developmental theories describe changes in mental abilities (cognition), social roles, moral reasoning, and beliefs about the nature of knowledge.

For example, educational psychologists have researched the instructional applicability of Jean Piaget's theory of development, according to which children mature through four stages of cognitive capability. **Piaget hypothesized** that children are not capable of abstract logical thought until they are older than about 11 years, and therefore younger children need to be taught using concrete objects and examples. Researchers have found that transitions, such as from concrete to abstract logical thought, do not occur at the same time in all domains. A child may be able to think abstractly about mathematics, but remain limited to concrete thought when reasoning about human relationships. Perhaps Piaget's most enduring contribution is his insight that people actively construct their understanding through a self-regulatory process.

Piaget proposed a developmental theory of moral reasoning in which children progress from a naive understanding of morality based on behavior and outcomes to a more advanced understanding based on intentions.

Piaget's views of moral development were elaborated by Kohlberg into a stage theory of moral development. There is evidence that the moral reasoning described in stage theories is not sufficient to account for moral behavior. For example, other factors such as modeling (as described by the social cognitive theory of morality) are required to explain bullying.

Rudolf Steiner's model of child development interrelates physical, emotional, cognitive, and moral development in developmental stages similar to those later described by Piaget.

Developmental theories are sometimes presented not as shifts between qualitatively different stages, but as gradual increments on separate dimensions. Development of epistemological beliefs (beliefs about knowledge) have been described in terms of gradual changes in people's belief in: certainty and permanence of knowledge, fixedness of ability, and credibility of authorities such as teachers and experts. People develop more sophisticated beliefs about knowledge as they gain in education and maturity.

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